

FOSTERING INFORMATION COMPETENCE THROUGH DIGITAL EDUCATION RESOURCES

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Abstract. *This article explores the importance of information and communication technologies (ICT) in developing students' information competence. It highlights the key aspects of building skills in searching, analyzing, processing, and effectively utilizing information in professional activities through the use of ICT tools. Additionally, the article provides a detailed discussion on the essential components and criteria necessary for fostering information competence, as well as indicators for measuring and evaluating its level. Information competence is regarded as a crucial tool for training highly qualified and competitive professionals who meet contemporary standards. The article also examines the advantages of incorporating electronic learning resources and distance education platforms into the educational process, along with the benefits of using information technology within the learning environment.*

Keywords: *information competence, information and communication technologies, electronic educational resources, computer programs, distance learning sites.*

Introduction: Modern information society is characterized by the creation of a single global information space, which enables wide access to information and production of various information resources by fully utilizing the potential of information and communication technologies (ICT). The goal of higher education is to train highly qualified and competitive specialists capable of effectively using ICT in their professional activities.

The tasks of the modern education system focus not on providing students with as much knowledge as possible, but on teaching them to select necessary information from vast data, to prepare intellectually developed, creative individuals, and to encourage independent engagement in various fields based on personal abilities.

Various researchers, including M.I. Bekoyeva, V.V. Grinshkun, S.G. Grigoryev, O.U. Gogitsayeva, G.S. Kubanseva, and Y.A. Nikitina, have conducted studies on forming students' information competence in higher education, emphasizing the ability to search, process, and make decisions based on information, along with modeling skills using computers in both standard and non-standard situations.

Main Part. Information competence reflects the ability to independently search for, analyze, select, process, and transmit necessary information through both oral and written communication using information technologies. The development of information competence begins in primary education and continues throughout higher education. In the information society, individuals must first organize acquired information and knowledge, highlighting what is essential to them. They should be able to manage various information flows, distinguish between old and new, assess primary and secondary matters, and effectively handle the information available to them.

The Evolution of Information Competence. Historically, information competence has evolved from basic literacy in using computers to a broader skill set involving the critical evaluation, management, and ethical use of information. With the digital transformation, this

competence has become essential across all fields. This section could delve into how digital literacy standards, like the Association of College & Research Libraries (ACRL) Standards, have shaped our understanding of information competence in academia.

Theoretical Frameworks and Models. To better understand information competence, several theoretical frameworks offer valuable insights. The Big6 Information Literacy Model, for instance, provides a structured approach that emphasizes task definition, information-seeking strategies, and synthesizing information for specific needs. You could discuss how these frameworks can be adapted to higher education settings, where students need to learn how to apply information skills in their professional fields.

Comparative Analysis of ICT Tools. ICT tools, such as learning management systems (LMS) like Moodle and Google Classroom, and collaborative platforms like Microsoft Teams and Zoom, play a pivotal role in developing information competence. This section could compare these tools, focusing on how each one facilitates different aspects of information competence. For example, Google Classroom may encourage collaboration, while Moodle offers robust tools for assessing students' progress in mastering information competencies.

Challenges in Developing Information Competence. Despite the benefits of ICT, challenges persist. A significant issue is the digital divide, which restricts access to information resources for some students. Additionally, educators may lack the training to fully integrate ICT into their teaching. This section could propose solutions, such as government initiatives to increase ICT access or professional development programs for educators to enhance their digital literacy skills.

Case Studies and Practical Applications. Including case studies provides concrete examples of how institutions are successfully implementing ICT-based programs. For instance, Stanford University uses simulation activities and e-learning resources to foster information competence in business and engineering programs. Another example could highlight how a specific course employs real-world applications, such as digital marketing assignments that require students to analyze and interpret data from online sources.

Future Trends in Information Competence. Emerging technologies like artificial intelligence (AI), machine learning, virtual reality (VR), and augmented reality (AR) are expected to revolutionize how students engage with information. This section could discuss these technologies' potential impact on information competence, such as VR simulations for medical students to practice diagnosing illnesses. Educators should consider these trends to prepare students for rapidly changing technological landscapes.

Impact on Career Readiness. Information competence is critical to career readiness in the digital age. For instance, professions in data science, digital marketing, and cybersecurity rely heavily on information competence. Citing research on the correlation between information competence and employability can further strengthen this section. Highlight how students with strong information competencies are better positioned to meet workforce demands, thus bridging the skills gap.

To be information-competent, a person must actively participate in communication processes. The ultimate goal of mastering information competence is to form an independent, creative individual who is self-aware and able to express themselves effectively. Personal information competence and society's information competence are interdependent and mutually

enriching. An individual's level of information competence correlates with societal competence, which is determined by the informational capacities of its structural units.

Information competence in students includes:

A set of knowledge necessary for solving professional problems creatively,

Various activity methods required for professional self-awareness,

Personal qualities, motivations, and needs aimed at enhancing personal competencies,

The ability to select the most important directions for themselves.

Implementing information competence in the educational process involves interactive learning approaches, such as computer simulations, business and role-playing games, practical exercises, and psychological training. Training sessions with experts from national and international companies, as well as government and public organizations, are also beneficial. The main goal of interactive learning sessions is to ensure that at least 70% of the total time allocated for a subject is dedicated to these methods.

When the educational process is designed to be as close to real-life activities as possible, it yields effective results in developing both information and other competencies. However, organizing such activities in the form of lectures and seminars presents challenges. Researchers like T.V. Komar and A.A. Korostelev have noted the importance of integrating computer and information cycles early in students' academic careers to familiarize them with the information needed in their future professional activities.

To achieve these goals, various electronic resources, such as e-learning modules, electronic textbooks, and network-based educational materials, should be utilized in the educational process, as highlighted by M.I. Bekoyeva. Working with electronic learning resources involves both group activities under the teacher's guidance and independent tasks, which help to solidify theoretical knowledge and expand intellectual skills.

In addition, electronic educational resources should incorporate online learning resources like edu.uz, hemis.uz, moodle.uz, ziyonet.uz, and others. During the teaching process, the teacher may introduce these platforms, providing brief descriptions for each one.

The use of ICT in education fosters personal qualities such as independence, creativity, and self-awareness among students. Creating presentations for class, conducting internet research for professional issues, and using educational materials help students acquire theoretical skills, promote interdisciplinary connections, and encourage self-directed learning.

Conclusion: In a broad sense, students' information competence refers to their ability to fully perceive realities in an information society, adapt to the opportunities available, and achieve self-awareness. Information competence is not predetermined but requires ongoing development and enhancement, which can be achieved through a higher education process that fosters these skills.

In modern higher education, it is essential to integrate the possibilities offered by information and communication technologies to train highly qualified professionals who can adapt to the rapidly changing realities of life. The criteria for forming students' information competence include:

The ability to effectively address educational and developmental tasks using ICT in line with the new pedagogical tools of the modern information society.

The readiness to adopt new software as part of the continuous process of educational modernization.

The ability to utilize ICT in professional activities.

Indicators for assessing the level of students' information competence include:

The ability to search, organize, assimilate, and transmit educational information using ICT tools;

Effective use of ICT tools in mastering university subjects;

Active utilization of ICT within the educational environment;

The capability to create and maintain educational material databases;

The ability to acquire new software products for solving professional tasks and assessing their quality and functionality.

Students' information competence can be evaluated through various methods such as completing control assignments, teacher assessments, surveys, testing knowledge, and monitoring laboratory work and independent projects.

In summary, as society continues to evolve, the importance of fostering information competence in students becomes increasingly clear. Mastering this skill enables students to integrate fully into the information society and adapt to its demands. Therefore, higher education institutions must prioritize developing these competencies by leveraging the educational potential of modern ICT.

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